

Supplemental Table 4. Data charting for all studies assessing the association between race/ethnicity and GWG.

Author	Year	Country	Study design	Source of GWG data; guideline used	Study population	Sample size	Significant findings	Non-significant findings	Race/ethnicity categories	Study sample primarily included individuals with a vulnerability factor?	Findings
Alhusen, J. L.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth from 2004-11 and completed the Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System survey	251 342	Odds of excessive GWG decreased if Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic or Asian non-Hispanic (as compared to White non-Hispanic); odds of insufficient GWG increased if Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic or Asian non-Hispanic (as compared to White non-Hispanic)	NS effect of non-Hispanic American Indian/Alaska Native on excessive or insufficient GWG	White non-Hispanic; Black non-Hispanic; Hispanic; American Indian/Alaska Native non-Hispanic; Asian non-Hispanic;	No	S & NS
Bahadoer S.	2015	Netherlands	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Multiethnic population-based cohort of women who were pregnant in Rotterdam from 2001-05	6 444	Surinamese-Hindustani and Moroccan women had lower risks of excessive GWG and lower GWG (vs. Dutch women)	NS difference between in total GWG for Cape Verdean, Dutch Antillean, Surinamese-Creole, and Turkish women vs Dutch women	Surinamese-Hindustani; Moroccan; Dutch; Cape Verdean; Antillean; Surinamese-Creole; Turkish	No	S & NS
Berenson, A. B.	1997	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Adolescents <18 years who received prenatal care at an adolescent obstetrics clinic (single-site)	337	Significant differences in proportion of women with GWG <20 lbs vs ≥20 lbs by race/ethnicity (Black, Mexican-American, White, other)		Black; White; Mexican-American; other	Yes	S
Beydoun, H. A.	2011	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Respondents of the 2000-06 Oklahoma Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System who were ≥20 years of age	11 561	Asian women had higher odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG)	NS difference in odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG) by race/ethnicity (White, Black, Native American, Asian); NS difference in odds of inadequate GWG (vs adequate GWG) by race/ethnicity for women who were White, Black, or Native American	White; Black; Native American; Asian	No	S & NS
Bogaerts, A.	2012	Belgium	Prospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women who delivered in Flanders in 2009	54 022	Higher odds of excessive GWG if Dutch or Turkish and lower odds in Moroccan (as compared to Belgian), lower odds of insufficient GWG if Turkish but higher odds if Moroccan (as compared to Belgian)	NS effect of Dutch ethnicity (compared to Belgian) on insufficient GWG	Belgian; Dutch; Turkish; Moroccan; other	No	S & NS
Cameron, R. P.	1996	USA	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Pregnant White and Black women (18-40 years old) from three obstetric clinics for low-income women	132	Weight deviation (calculated on the basis of recommended weight for height and adjusted for medically ideal weight gain during pregnancy) increased significantly for Black women from prepregnancy to the 2nd trimester, but remained constant for White		Black; White [Terminology used in study: European American, African American]	Yes	S
Caulfield, L. E.	1996	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Black and White women who delivered at John Hopkins Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics from 1987-89	3 870	Increased risk of insufficient GWG if Black	NS effect of being Black on excessive GWG	White; Black	No	S & NS
Cavicchia, P. P.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in South Carolina from 2004-06	132 574	Significant differences in adequacy of GWG between racial/ethnic groups (no post-hoc tests)		White non-Hispanic; Black non-Hispanic; Hispanic	No	S

Chagarla mudi, H.	2018	USA	Retrospective Medical records; IOM 2009	Women attending an outpatient obstetrics/ gynecology clinic that mainly serves a low- income community (2012- 13) in North Carolina	410		NS effect on odds of having excessive or insufficient GWG (as compared to adequate GWG) by race/ethnicity (White, Black, Hispanic/other)	White; Black; Hispanic or other	Yes	NS
Chang, T.	2017	USA	Retrospective Medical records; IOM 2009	Women aged 15-24 years living in large US cities from 1998-2000; national weights were used to make data representative of births in all large US cities (populations of >200,000); all women were part of the "Fragile Families and Child Wellbeing Study"	1,034 (unweighted)	Hispanic women had lower risk of excessive GWG than non-Hispanic women	NS association between race/ethnicity (Black or other as compared to White) and excessive or insufficient GWG; Hispanic ethnicity not associated to insufficient GWG	White; Black; Hispanic; other	No	S & NS
Cheng, H. R.	2015	USA	Retrospective Birth certificate; IOM 2009	White non-Hispanic and Asian non-Hispanic (Asian Indian, Chinese, Filipino, Japanese, Korean, or Vietnamese) women who were documented in the 2009 Texas birth certificate data	114 632	Asian-American women had a higher risk of insufficient GWG and a lower risk of excessive GWG (vs. White non-Hispanic); among Asian women: high risk of insufficient GWG in Asian Indian, Filipino, Japanese, Korean and Vietnamese (as compared to Chinese); higher risk of excessive GWG in Asians who are unmarried, have some college education (as compared to high school or less) and primiparous; lower risk of excessive GWG in Asians who are foreign-born	NS difference in risk of excessive GWG according to Asian subgroup	White non-Hispanic; Asian-American non- Hispanic; subgroups of Asian-American: Asian Indian, Chinese, Filipino, Japanese, Korean, Vietnamese	No	S & NS
Chihara, I.	2014	USA	Retrospective Self-reported ; IOM 2009	Low income women who were enrolled in Hawaii's Special Supplemental Nutrition Program for Women, Infants, and Children from 2003-05	19 130	Significant difference in GWG adequacy based on race/ethnicity (Hawaiian/part Hawaiian, Asian, White, Pacific Islander, other)		Hawaiian/part Hawaiian; Asian; White; Pacific Islander; other	Yes	S
Cohen, A. K.	2016	USA	Retrospective Self-reported; IOM 2009	Participants of the 1979 National Longitudinal Survey of Youth who were 14-22 years old in 1979	2 769	Less education protected against excessive GWG among Black women (less than a high school degree vs high school degree); White women with less than a high school degree were more likely to have excessive GWG than those who graduated high school and those with a college degree	NS interaction by race/ethnicity on odds of insufficient GWG by educational attainment; NS effect of education on excessive GWG in Hispanic or overweight women; NS difference in odds of excessive GWG if high school degree vs college degree for all race/ethnicities	White/other; Black; Hispanic	No	S & NS

Cruikshank, A.	2018	Australia	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Women ≥18 years who delivered at a hospital in a socially disadvantaged area south of Brisbane	399	Significant differences in GWG adequacy, with Maori and Pasifika women more likely to report excessive GWG (vs. other groups); Maori and Pasifika women also had significantly higher GWG		Maori and Pasifika; other (included English and European, Asian, Aboriginal/Torres Strait Islander, and African)	No	S
Cunningham, S.D.	2018	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women age 14-21 yrs old enrolled in the CenteringPregnancy Plus RCT (a multi-site prenatal care intervention) from 2008-2012; hospitals chosen for the RCT primarily served women who have low income and women from minority groups	505		Women having adequate vs excessive GWG did not differ by race/ethnicity (Latina, Black non-Latina, or other)	Latina; Black non-Latina; other	Yes	NS
Deputy, N. P.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Participants of the 2010-11 Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System	44 421	<u>Normal weight</u> : higher odds of insufficient GWG if Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic, Asian (as compared to White non-Hispanic); lower odds of excessive GWG if Asian <u>Overweight</u> : higher odds of insufficient GWG if Black non-Hispanic, Alaskan Native (compared to White non-Hispanic) <u>Obese</u> : lower odds of insufficient GWG if Asian, Alaskan Native; lower odds of excessive if Alaskan Native	Race/ethnicity: NS effect on GWG adequacy in any BMI group for Native American, Hawaiian, and other	White non-Hispanic; Black non-Hispanic; Hispanic; Asian; Native American; Alaska Native; Hawaiian (including part Hawaiian); other	No	S & NS
Fernandez, I. D.	2011	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Population registry of adolescents who gave birth in Upstate New York from 1996-2002	6 995	Significant differences in total GWG by race (White, Black, other)		White; Black; other	Yes	S
Fontaine, P. L.	2012	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Black and White women age 18-40 years who gave birth from 2004-07 in the Minneapolis-St. Paul metropolitan area	2 760	Adjusted multivariate analysis: White women had significantly greater total GWG compared to Black women (seen in normal weight, overweight and obese categories); significant difference in GWG adequacy between White and Black women (for normal, overweight, and obese)	NS difference in total GWG and GWG adequacy by race in underweight women	White; Black	No	S & NS
Gaillard, R.	2013	Netherlands	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with pregnant women in Rotterdam from 2001-05	6 959	Lower odds of excessive GWG if Non-European (vs Dutch/European ethnicity)		Dutch/European; non-European (Surinamese, Turkish, Moroccan, Cape Verdian/Dutch Antilles, Other)	No	S

Galin, J.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who delivered in California from 2007-12	2 364 793	Living in neighbourhoods with the highest quartile of violence was associated with excessive GWG (vs lowest quartile of violence) across all race/ethnicities; Asian/Pacific Islander and Hispanic had higher risk of excessive GWG in all levels of neighbourhood violence (when compared to low neighbourhood violence); decreased risk of insufficient GWG if neighbourhood violence only seen with Asian/Pacific Islanders non-Hispanic, and increased risk of insufficient GWG if multi-race non-Hispanic for neighbourhoods with low-medium and high levels of violence	NS difference in GWG adequacy by levels of neighbourhood violence for all other race/ethnicities	White non-Hispanic; Black non-Hispanic; Native American non-Hispanic; Asian/Pacific Islander non-Hispanic; two or more races, non-Hispanic (multi-race); Hispanic	No	S & NS
Gillespie, S. L.	2016	USA	Prospective	Medical record and measured; no GWG guideline identified	White and Black women who attended a university medical center or were from the surrounding community	105		NS difference in GWG by 2nd trimester and in total GWG between Black and White women	White; Black	No	NS
Groth, S. W.	2018	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	White and Black women aged 18-35 with a BMI between 18.5 and 34.9 kg/m ² who participated in a RCT from 2009-14	774	Multiparous women had lower GWG than primiparous women when all BMI groups analyzed together (true for both gene groups); among Black women: low-income women (<185% of poverty line) with obesity gained significantly more weight than higher income women (>185% of poverty line) with obesity in one of two gene groups (FTO gene), but this difference was not observed among other BMI groups or when all BMI groups were combined; among White women: higher income normal-weight women had significantly lower weight gain in both gene groups (FTO and GNB3), but this difference was not observed in other BMI groups or when all BMI groups were combined	In most BMI groups and gene groups, income was not significantly associated with GWG for Black and White women; when parity was divided by BMI, differences in GWG did not remain significant (for all groups)	Black; White [Terminology used in study: African American, Caucasian]	No	S & NS
Haeri, S.	2010	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 1990	All births to adolescents at a single site from 2000-04	456		NS difference in adequate vs excessive GWG by race/ethnicity (Black, Hispanic, White)	White; Black; Hispanic	Yes	NS
Haile, Z. T.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Participants of the population-based Infant Feeding Practices Study II from 2005-07	2 053	Significant differences in GWG adequacy by race/ethnicity (White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic, other), education (high school or less, some college, college graduate), poverty-to-income ratio (<185%, 185-349%, 350%+)		White non-Hispanic; Black non-Hispanic; Hispanic; other	No	S

Headen, I.	2018	USA	Prospective	Self-reported ; IOM 2009	Participants of the 1979 National Longitudinal Survey of Youth who were 14-21 years old in 1979	3 300	Significant differences in GWG adequacy according to race/ethnicity (White, Black or Hispanic/Latino/Spanish); higher average cumulative neighbourhood deprivation was associated with increased risk of insufficient GWG (did not vary by ethnicity) and excessive GWG (only for White women); upward mobility was associated with decreased risk of insufficient GWG across all ethnicities		Black; Hispanic/Latino/Spanish; White/other (note: this group is 88% white, with the other 22% including all other non-Black, non-Latino women)	No	S
Headen, I.	2015	USA	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth from 1979-2010 (all were part of the National Longitudinal Survey of Youth)	3 835	Black and Hispanic women had higher risk of insufficient GWG than White women (when divided into BMI categories, this remained true for all normal weight women; for underweight women: only true for Black women; for overweight and obese: risk of insufficient GWG did not vary by race/ethnicity)	NS effect of race/ethnicity on risk of excessive GWG	Black; White; Hispanic	No	S & NS
Hediger, M. L.	1990	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified	Low-income adolescents registered in the Camden County Adolescent Family Life program from 1982-87	1 419	White had significantly higher GWG (vs. Black and Puerto Rican)		Black; White; Puerto Rican	Yes	S
Hediger, M. L.	1989	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; based on clinical standards	Low-income adolescents registered in the Camden County Adolescent Family Life program from 1982-87	1 790	Significant differences in total GWG by race/ethnicity (Puerto Rican, Black, White), with White women gaining significantly more weight		Black; White; Puerto Rican	Yes	S
Held, M. L.	2018	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; no GWG guideline identified	Undocumented Latina immigrant women (≥ 18 years old) from Guatemala or Mexico who gave birth in Nebraska from 2007-11	4 188	Excessive GWG more prevalent in Mexican than Guatemalan immigrants		Guatemalan immigrant; Mexican immigrant	Yes	S
Hernandez-Rivas, E.	2013	Spain	Prospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Single-site study involving women who were monitored prenatally and gave birth from 2004-11	456		NS difference in total GWG by race/ethnicity (White vs Latin American, South-Central Asian, Moroccan, or East Asian)	White; Latin American; South-Central Asian; Moroccan; East Asian	No	NS
Herring, S. J.	2012	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Urban, low-income, primarily Black women seeking prenatal care at a university hospital from 2009-11	94		NS association between excessive GWG and race/ethnicity (Black vs other)	Black/African American;	Yes	NS

Hickey, C. A.	1992b	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; GWG evaluated as a percent of standard W/H (Rosso, 1985)	Low-income, Black and Hispanic women enrolled in prenatal care at two university-operated clinics	150	Women who were Black were at increased risk of low GWG (<120% of standard prepregnancy weight for height); in preliminary analysis higher education increased risk of low GWG, but in univariate analysis education was only significant for Hispanic women; in univariate analysis, marital status was significantly associated with GWG in Hispanic women (but NS for Black women), but was dropped from later multivariate models as it was a poor predictor of GWG when other variables were entered in model	Black; Hispanic	Yes	S
Hickey, C. A.	1997a	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Low-income, multiparous Black and White women with one or more risk factors for fetal growth restriction, who enrolled in prenatal care at specific university-operated clinics from 1985-88	806	Among Black women, having a mistimed or unwanted pregnancy, caring for more than one preschooler at home, and not having a car for errands were associated with increased odds of insufficient GWG (≤ 10 kg); among White women, those who worked over 40hrs/week had an increased odds of insufficient GWG	Black; White	Yes	S
Hickey, C. A.	1993	USA	Prospective	Mesured; IOM 1990	Multi-site study involving Black or White women with a low-income who were pregnant with their 2nd or 3rd child and who were at risk of having a small-for-gestational-age infant	1 168	NS difference in total GWG between Black and White women	White; Black	Yes	NS
Hoff, C.	1985	USA	Retrospective	Measured; no GWG guidelines identified	Nulliparous, primarily Black, low-income adolescents (< 17 years) and adults (17-31 years) who gave birth at a specific hospital in South Alabama from 1974-79	1 844	Adults: higher GWG in White women than Black women NS difference in GWG between adults and adolescents of same race; in adolescents: NS difference in GWG between Black and White	Black; White	Yes	S & NS
Hollard, A. L.	2006	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified	Multi-site study with Black, White, and Hispanic women who had a previous cesarean section delivery and gave birth a second time from 1997-2002 in Southern California	5 589	Significant differences in prevalence of high GWG (>13.6 kg) by racial/ethnic group (White, Hispanic, Black)	White; Black; Hispanic [Terminology used in study: Caucasian, African American]	No	S

Hollingsworth, D. R.	1976	USA	Prospective	Not specified; no GWG guideline used	Unmarried, low-income, primiparous adolescents (age 12-18) who were admitted to a young mothers medical-obstetric service from 1971-74	406	Among adolescents with preeclampsia, White women had significantly higher total GWG than Black women	Among normal pregnancies (without complications and infants born of normal weight), there was no significant difference in total GWG between Black and White adolescents	Black; White	Yes	S & NS
Howie, L. D.	2003	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	Women included in the 2000 US Natality File (excluding women from California, as GWG there is not collected)	2 796 805	Lower odds of excessive GWG if women were of a racial/ethnic minority group (Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic/Latina, other vs White non-Hispanic)		Black non-Hispanic; White non-Hispanic; Hispanic/Latina; other	No	S
Huynh, M.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Primiparous women who gave birth from 1999-2001 in New York City, were ≥20 years old, and either White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, or Hispanic	56 911	Excessive GWG more likely in Black non-Hispanic or Hispanic women than in White non-Hispanic women; lower odds of excessive GWG if White non-Hispanic with college or more education; Hispanic women with high school or more education had higher risk of excessive GWG than those with less than high school education	NS difference in prevalence of excessive GWG between highest and lowest levels of education (college or more vs less than high school education) when not divided by race/ethnicity and neighborhood SES; prevalence of excessive GWG did not vary by education level in Black non-Hispanic women, while White non-Hispanic women did not have a significant difference between high school education or some college when compared to less than high school education	White non-Hispanic; Black non-Hispanic; Hispanic	No	S & NS
Incollingo Rodriguez, A. C.	2019	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women enrolled in the multi-site Community Child Health Network study who indicated that they experience everyday discrimination due to their weight or height	214		NS difference in odds of excessive GWG or total GWG according to race/ethnicity; NS difference in prevalence of excess GWG or in total GWG between racial/ethnic groups (White non Hispanic, Black, Latina)	Black; White non-Hispanic; Latina	No	NS
Khanolkar, A. R.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Medical record/birth certificate; IOM 2009	All women who gave birth in Washington State from 2006-08	181 948	Significant difference in adequacy of GWG according to ethnicity (White, Black, Native American, East Asian, Hispanic, South Asian, Hawaiian/Pacific Islander/other); total GWG also varied significantly between racial/ethnic groups		White; Black; Native American; East Asian; Hispanic; South Asian; Hawaiian/Pacific; Islander/other	No	S
Kieffer, E. C.	2001	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Black and Latina women in Detroit who received at least 4 prenatal care visits from January 1995 - December 1998	1 334	Higher odds of insufficient and lower odds of excessive GWG in Latina vs Black women; Black women had significantly higher GWG than Latina women		Latina; Black [Terminology used in study: African American]	Yes	S

Kinnunen, T. I.	2016	Norway	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with pregnant women seeking prenatal care in Eastern Oslo from 2008-10	632	Eastern European had higher total GWG (as compared to Western European)	NS difference in odds of excessive GWG between racial/ethnic groups; NS difference in GWG between Western European and South Asian, East Asian, Middle Eastern or African	Eastern European; Middle Eastern (includes North African and Central Asian); African (except North Africa); Western European (includes North American); South Asian; East Asian	No	S & NS
Koh, H.	2013	Singapore	Retrospective	Medical record; GWG guideline by Wong et al., 2000	All women who delivered at a specific hospital from Jan-Apr 2008 (approximately 30% of infants in Singapore are delivered at this hospital every year)	1 166	Higher odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate): ethnicity (Malay vs Chinese); higher odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate): ethnicity (Malay vs Chinese)	NS difference in GWG adequacy between Indian and Chinese ethnicities	Malay; Chinese; Indian	No	S & NS
Kominari, M. A.	2018b	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Large multi-site study with random selection of women who gave birth at one of the sites from 2008-11	29 861	Significant differences in GWG adequacy (inadequate, adequate, excessive) according to race/ethnicity (White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, Asian non-Hispanic, Hispanic, other)		Black non-Hispanic; White non-Hispanic; Asian non-Hispanic; Hispanic; other/unknown	No	S
Kowal, C.	2012	Canada	Retrospective	Self-reported; Health Canada 2010 (IOM 2009)	Respondents of the Canadian Maternity Experiences Survey of 2006, all of whom were ≥15 years old	6,233 (weighted to n=74,523)		NS difference in odds of GWG adequacy (insufficient or excessive vs adequate) according to ethnicity	Aboriginal; British Isles/French; European; North American; other	No	NS
Krukowski, R. A.	2013	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Black and White respondents of the Arkansas Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2004-08 who had adequate or excessive GWG	4 619	Lower odds of excessive GWG if Black (vs White), Hispanic (vs not)		Hispanic; White; Black [Terminology used in study: African American, Caucasian]	No	S
Larouche, M.	2010	Canada	Retrospective	Medical record; Health Canada 2010 (IOM 2009)	Women who delivered at a health centre in Montreal from January 1998 - December 2007	960	Latin American had significantly higher GWG than South Asian	NS difference in all GWG between all other racial/ethnic groups (Caucasian, Black, East Asian, West Asian/Arab)	White; Black; Latin American; East Asian; West Asian/Arab; South Asian [Terminology used in study: Caucasian]	No	S & NS
Leonard, S. A.	2017	USA	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Women who were enrolled in the National Longitudinal Survey of Youth 1979 and gave birth from 1979-2012	7 539	Significant difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate or excessive) by race/ethnicity (White non-Hispanic/other, Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic)		White non-Hispanic/other; Black non-Hispanic; Hispanic	No	S

Lindberg, S.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women who delivered at UW Health from 2007-12	7 385	Decreased odds of excessive GWG: Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic, or other non-Hispanic race/ethnicity (vs White non-Hispanic); factors increasing odds of insufficient GWG: Black non-Hispanic or other non-Hispanic race/ethnicity (as compared to White non-Hispanic), Medicaid (compared to commercial insurance), neighborhood with high economic hardship (compared to moderate)	NS effect of Hispanic ethnicity (vs White non-Hispanic) on odds of insufficient GWG	Black non-Hispanic; White non-Hispanic; Hispanic; other non-Hispanic	No	S & NS
Liu, J.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Black non-Hispanic, White non-Hispanic, or Hispanic women without prepregnancy hypertension who gave birth from 2004-06 in South Carolina	133 849	Higher odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) in Hispanic and Black women (only in women who were underweight or had a normal BMI; Hispanic and Black non-Hispanic were compared to White non-Hispanic); lower odds of insufficient GWG in overweight Hispanic women; lower odds of excessive GWG in Black non-Hispanic (all BMI) and Hispanic (except underweight)	NS difference in odds of excessive vs adequate GWG in underweight Hispanic (as compared to underweight White non-Hispanic); NS difference in insufficient vs adequate GWG in overweight/obese Black non-Hispanic and obese Hispanic (as compared to White non-Hispanic)	White non-Hispanic; Black non-Hispanic; Hispanic	No	S & NS
Longmore, D. K.	2018	Australia	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	White and Indigenous women; women with hyperglycemia were recruited through the NT Diabetes in Pregnancy Clinical Register, while a representative sample of women without hyperglycemia were recruited through antenatal clinics	877	Excessive GWG more prevalent in White, while insufficient GWG more prevalent in Indigenous (both outcomes only significant in women without hyperglycemia)	NS difference in GWG adequacy between Indigenous and White women who had maternal hyperglycemia	Indigenous; White [Terminology used in study: Europid]	No	S & NS
Loris, P.	1985	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; Morse et al. 1975 (standard GWG curve)	Adolescents age 13-19 years in the Sacramento area who attended adolescent-specific pregnancy clinics or programs from 1979 -82	145		NS difference in total GWG based on ethnic group (White, Hispanic, Black)	Black; Hispanic; White [Terminology used in study: Anglo]	Yes	NS
Lowell, H.	2010	Canada	Retrospective	Self-reported; Health Canada 1999 IOM (1990)	Respondents of the 2006 national Maternity Experiences Survey, all of whom were ≥15 years old	5 554	Significantly higher prevalence of excessive GWG in Aboriginal women	NS difference in prevalence of insufficient GWG according to Aboriginal status	Aboriginal; non-Aboriginal	No	S & NS
Margerison-Zilko, C.	2014	USA	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Participants of the 1979 National Longitudinal Survey of Youth, all of whom were 14-22 years of age in 1979	5 175	Effect of extreme unexpected economic contraction differed by race/ethnicity: increased risk of insufficient and excessive GWG if Black non-Hispanic or Hispanic (vs non-Black/non-Hispanic)		Hispanic; Black/non-Hispanic; non-Black/non-Hispanic	No	S

Marsiglio, W.	1988	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; GWG ≤15lbs considered insufficient, ≥50lbs excessive	Women who participated in the National Longitudinal Survey of Labour Market Experience of Youth; sample weighted to be representative of a national cross-section of women age 19-27 years in 1984; women were primiparous at the time of their interview	6 015	Predictors of insufficient GWG: being Black (vs non Black)	NS effect of being Black on excessive GWG; NS effect on insufficient or excessive GWG if Hispanic ethnicity, if White and economically disadvantaged (results not indicated for other racial groups)	Black; White; Hispanic	No	S & NS
Mehta, U.	2011	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Participants of the PIN study (Pregnancy, Infection and Nutrition study) who attended prenatal care at University of North Carolina hospitals from January 2001 - June 2005; all women were >16 years	1 192	Higher total GWG in White women (as compared to Black women) and higher mean adequacy of GWG in Black women (calculated as observed GWG/expected GWG)		Black; White [Terminology used in study: African American, Caucasian]	No	S
Mendez, D. D.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Black non-Hispanic and White non-Hispanic women who gave birth in Allegheny County, Pennsylvania from 2003-10	55 608	Association between neighborhood socioeconomic disadvantage (NSED) and gestational weight loss: for White non-Hispanic, all levels of NSED compared to low NSED were associated with gestational weight loss (vs adequate GWG), while for Black non-Hispanic only high NSED compared to low NSED was associated with gestational weight loss	NS association between mid-low or mid-high NSED (vs low) on gestational weight loss (vs adequate GWG) in Black non-Hispanic women	Black non-Hispanic; White non-Hispanic	No	S & NS
Mendez, D. D.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Black non-Hispanic and White non-Hispanic women who gave birth in Allegheny County, Pennsylvania from 2003-10	73 061	White non-Hispanic women, but not Black non-Hispanic, had increased prevalence ratio for insufficient GWG if living in neighborhood with mid-high and high poverty (compared to low poverty); White non-Hispanic living in predominantly black or mixed neighborhoods were more likely to have insufficient GWG (vs White non-Hispanic women living in low % Black/predominantly White non-Hispanic neighborhoods)	NS relationship between neighborhood racial composition and GWG for Black women	Black non-Hispanic; White non-Hispanic	No	S & NS
Messer, L. C.	2012	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	White non-Hispanic and Black non-Hispanic women who gave birth in one of four counties in North Carolina from 2001-05	23 533	Brief description of findings: higher odds of insufficient GWG: living in a neighborhood with higher physical incivilities, living in a neighborhood with more social space (only for White non-Hispanic); lower odds of insufficient GWG in neighborhood with higher walkability (only significant in one neighborhood-level for White non-Hispanic, but all levels for Black non-Hispanic)		White non-Hispanic; Black non-Hispanic [Terminology used in study: non-Hispanic African American]	No	S

Misra, V. K.	2010	USA	Prospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Women who participated in the Behaviour in Pregnancy Study (BIPS) in Los Angeles; all were ≥18 years of age	435	Black women (as compared to non-Black women) had significantly higher rate of GWG in first half of pregnancy	NS difference in rate of GWG between Black and non-Black from 16-20 weeks pregnancy to 30-36 weeks of pregnancy	Black; non-Black [Terminology used in study: African American, non-African American]	No	S & NS
Morris, D. L.	1992	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate or medical record; Loris et al. 1985	White, Black, and Hispanic adolescents (≤17 years) who delivered at a University Hospital from January 1985 - December 1996	1 080	Significant difference in total GWG between White and Black women, with higher GWG in White	NS difference in total GWG for Hispanic vs Black or White	Hispanic; Black; White [Terminology used in study: black, Anglo, Hispanic]	Yes	S & NS
Most, J.	2018	USA	Prospective	Measured; no guideline identified	Women with obesity (BMI ≥30), between the ages of 18 and 40, who identified as Black non-Hispanic or White non-Hispanic	66		NS difference in rate of GWG in 2nd trimester (in g/week) between Black non-Hispanic and White non-Hispanic women	Black non-Hispanic; White non-Hispanic	No	NS
Naiqiso, S. L. S	2019	New Zealand	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Women enrolled in prenatal care with Counties Manukau Health from September 2004 - March 2016	604	Maori had higher odds of insufficient GWG; Pacific had higher odds of excessive GWG, while Indian had lower odds of excessive GWG (all racial/ethnic groups compared to European)	NS difference in odds of excessive or insufficient GWG between Asian and White women; NS difference in odds of insufficient GWG for Indian and Pacific women (vs European women); NS difference in odds of excessive GWG for Maori (vs European)	European; Maori; Asian; Indian; Pacific	No	S & NS
Nunnery, D.	2018	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women attending a WIC clinic (for low-income women) in 2014 who were receiving WIC as a maternity client and were ≥18 years old	160	Predictors of excessive GWG (higher odds): being Black (compared to not Black)		Black; Non-Black [Terminology used in study: African American, not African American]	Yes	S
Ochsenbein-Kolble, N.	2007	Switzerland and	Cross-sectional	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	White, Asian, and Black women at the Obstetric Outpatient Department at Zurich University Hospital from January 1996 - February 2000	4 034	Significantly lower GWG in Asian and Black (as compared to White); among White women: parity had a significant effect on GWG (effect on other race/ethnicities not noted)	NS effect of age on GWG in White women (effect on other race/ethnicities not noted)	Asian (primarily Sri Lankan, Thai, and Filipino); Black; White [Terminology used in study: Caucasian]	No	S & NS
Pawlak, M.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in Colorado from 2007-10	230 698	Increased odds of insufficient GWG in Hispanic, Black, and other race/ethnicity (vs White non-Hispanic); decreased odds of excessive GWG if Hispanic or other (compared to White non-Hispanic)	NS effect on excessive GWG if Black (vs White non-Hispanic)	White non-Hispanic; Black; Hispanic; other	No	S & NS
Platner, M. H.	2019	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in New York City from 2008-2012	515 148	Significant differences in adequacy of GWG based on race/ethnicity (Black non-Hispanic, White non-Hispanic, Puerto Rican, other Hispanic, Asian/Pacific Islander, other, non-Hispanic with two or more races)		Black non-Hispanic; White non-Hispanic; Puerto Rican; other Hispanic; Asian/Pacific Islander; other; non-Hispanic with two or more races	No	S

Rambouskova, J.	2009	Czech Republic	Prospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified	Multi-site study involving women who gave birth from 2000-2002; study included Roma women (an ethnic minority in the Czech Republic) and non-Roma women	227		NS difference in total GWG by race/ethnicity (Roma vs non-Roma)	Roma (ethnic minority); non-Roma	No	NS
Ratan, B. M.	2019	USA	Retrospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Low-income women with obesity who enrolled in prenatal care at a specific clinic in Houston, Texas from September 2013 August 2017; all women were receiving social assistance (CHIP Perinate or Medicaid)	772		NS difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, excessive) according to race/ethnicity (Black, Hispanic, White, Asian)	Black; White; Hispanic; Asian [Terminology used in study: African American, Caucasian]	Yes	NS
Restall, A.	2014	New Zealand, Australia, Ireland	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Multi-site cohort study with nulliparous women from 2004-11	1 950		NS difference in adequacy of GWG (not excessive vs excessive) according to ethnicity (White, Asian, Polynesian, Indian, other)	White; Asian; Polynesian (Maori & Pacific Islander); Indian; other [Terminology used in study: Caucasian]	No	NS
Rosal, M. C.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Multi-site study involving Non-Latina White and Latina women	571	Lower odds of excessive GWG in Latina (as compared to White non-Latina)	NS difference in odds of insufficient GWG between White non-Latina and Latina women	Latina; White non-Latina	No	S & NS
Rosenberg, T. J.	2005	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	Asian non-Hispanic, Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, and White non-Hispanic women who gave birth in New York City from 1999-2001	329 988	Significant differences in excessive GWG by race/ethnicity (compared prevalence of GWG <41 lbs vs 41+ lbs between Black non-Hispanic, White non-Hispanic, Asian non-Hispanic, and Hispanic)		Black non-Hispanic; White non-Hispanic; Asian non-Hispanic; Hispanic	No	S
Sackoff, J. E.	2015	USA	Cross-sectional	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Nulliparous women who gave birth in New York City from 1994-2004 and had a second pregnancy during that period; all women were either Black non-Hispanic, White non-Hispanic, Hispanic, or Asian/Pacific Islander	115 651	Significantly lower GWG in Asian/Pacific Islanders (as compared to White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic) and lower proportion of Asian/Pacific Islander women with GWG ≥40 lbs and ≥50 lbs (As compared to other 3 groups)	Similar total GWG for White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, and Hispanic, and similar proportions of women gaining ≥40 lbs and ≥50 lbs	Black non-Hispanic; White non-Hispanic; Hispanic; Asian/Pacific Islander	No	S & NS
Scholl, T. O.	1995	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Women age 12-29 with a low-income and a normal BMI; most women were Puerto Rican Hispanic or Black (data from Camden Study)	274		NS association between adequacy of GWG rate and race/ethnicity (Puerto-Rican, Black, White)	Puerto-Rican; Black; White	Yes	NS

Shieh, C.	2014	USA	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; trimester-specific GWG guideline from Fontaine et al. 2012	Black and Hispanic women ≥ 18 years of age enrolled in prenatal care at one of two health centers in a large Midwest city from August 2012 - January 2013	56	Excessive GWG more likely in Black (vs Hispanic)	NS difference in total GWG between Black and Hispanic	Black; Hispanic	Yes	S & NS
Shrestha, D.	2019	USA	Prospective	Measured and medical records; IOM 2009	Women enrolled in the National Institute of Child Health and Human Development Fetal Growth Study from July 2009 - January 2013; women were either non-Hispanic White, non-Hispanic Black, Hispanic, or Asian/Pacific Islander	1 945	GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate, excessive) varied by race/ethnicity (White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic, Asian/Pacific Islander)		White non-Hispanic; Black non-Hispanic; Asian/Pacific Islander; Hispanic	No	S
Siega-Riz, A. M.	1997	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Hispanic, primarily low-income women attending public prenatal clinics and who participated in a prematurity prevention project	6 114	Multivariate linear regression model for total GWG: positive association with being a US-born Hispanic	NS association between total GWG (for all women) and being of Mexican descent NS effect on odds of insufficient GWG (for all women): being of Mexican descent, being a US-born Hispanic	US-born Hispanic; Mexican descent; other Hispanic	Yes	S & NS
Singh, G. K.	2018	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; no GWG guideline identified	Women who gave birth in the USA in 2014-15 and were included in the national nativity files	7 966 573	Excessive GWG (>40lbs) significantly more prevalent in Samoan, Hawaiian, Cuban, Puerto Rican, White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic and American Indian/American Native compared to all Asian subgroups (Chinese, Japanese, Filipino, Asian Indian, Korean, Vietnamese)		Black non-Hispanic; White non-Hispanic; Alaska Native/American Indian; Chinese; Japanese; Filipino; Hawaiian; Asian Indian; Korean; Vietnamese; Samoan; other Asian/Pacific Islander; Mexican; Puerto Rican; Cuban; Central & South American; other Hispanic	No	S
Sowers, M. F.	2000	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Adolescents and adults participating in a study of pregnancy and lactation in Camden, New Jersey	252		NS difference in total GWG by race/ethnicity (White, Black, Hispanic)	White; Black; Hispanic	No	NS
Stogianni, A.	2019	Sweden	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guidelines identified	Women with and without diabetes who were admitted to a specific hospital in Kronoberg from January 2009 - December 2012	280		Among women with diabetes or without diabetes, ethnicity (Asian or Black vs White) was not significantly associated with high GWG (GWG ≥ 8 kg)	Asian; Black; White [Terminology used: African, Caucasian]	No	NS

Stotland, N. E.	2006	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 1990	Women with a normal or low pre-pregnancy BMI who gave birth at the University of California, San Francisco Medical Center from 1976 to 2001	15 101	Significant difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate, excessive) between racial/ethnic groups (White, Black, Latina, Asian) based on kg gained per week; no post-hoc analysis conducted	White; Black; Latina; Asian [Terminology used: African American]	No	S
Tabet, M.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Adolescents (<20 years old) who gave birth in the USA in 2012	171 573	Significant differences in adequacy of GWG (insufficient, adequate, excessive) between women of different racial/ethnic groups (White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, American Indian, Asian, Hispanic)	Black non-Hispanic; White non-Hispanic; American Indian; Asian; Hispanic	Yes	S
Vinikoor-Imler, L. C.	2011	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	Black non-Hispanic and White non-Hispanic women who gave birth from 2001-05 in one of four counties North Carolina and were enrolled in the third Pregnancy, Infection, and Nutrition Study (PIN3)	23 304	Insufficient GWG (<15 lbs) more likely if higher quartiles of social space [only in White non-Hispanic]; lower odds of inappropriate GWG if neighborhoods have high walkability; excessive or insufficient (for Black non-Hispanic: only insufficient) GWG associated with neighborhoods having high amounts of physical incivility	Black non-Hispanic; White non-Hispanic	No	S
Virji, S. K.	1991	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; no GWG guideline identified	A portion of women who had a live birth in 1980 in the US and were recorded in the National Natality Survey; births that resulted in adoption and births of non-US residents were excluded; women with low birthweight infants were intentionally oversampled	5 823	Significant differences in GWG (<20 lb vs >20 lb) between White and Black women, with lower GWG (<20 lbs) more common in Black	White; Black	No	S
Walker, L. O.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Hispanic and White non-Hispanic women who gave birth in 2009 in Texas and were ≥18 years old	250 857	Increased odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) if Hispanic (vs White non-Hispanic); decreased odds of excessive GWG if Hispanic (vs White non-Hispanic)	White non-Hispanic; Hispanic	No	S
Walker, L. O.	2002	USA	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Women who delivered at a single hospital with a parity of 3 or less and who had Medicaid coverage for prenatal care	305	NS difference in total GWG by race/ethnicity (White, Black, Hispanic)	White; Black; Hispanic [Terminology used in study: African American]	Yes	NS
Wells, C. S.	2006	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	Respondents of the 2000-02 Colorado Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System	4 528	NS effect of ethnicity (Hispanic, Black, other each compared to White non-Hispanic) on adequacy of GWG	White non-Hispanic; Black; Hispanic; other	No	NS

Woolfolk, C. L.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Population-based cohort of adolescents who gave birth in the USA in 2012	211 403	Significant difference in GWG adequacy according to race/ethnicity (White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic, other non-Hispanic)		White non-Hispanic; Black non-Hispanic; Hispanic; other non-Hispanic	Yes	S
Wright, C.	2013	USA	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Low-income urban women enrolled in a community-based participatory research study; all women attended a social service and advocacy agency for low-income women	101	Hispanic women were significantly more likely to have adequate GWG than excessive GWG	NS difference in GWG category (adequate vs excessive) by race/ethnicity (for White and Black only)	White; Black; Hispanic	Yes	S & NS
Zheng, Z.	2019	USA	Retrospective	Medical records or self-reported; IOM 2009	Women from the Boston Birth Cohort	5 568	Black non-Hispanic had lowest total GWG (as compared to White non-Hispanic, after controlling for confounders)		White non-Hispanic; Black non-Hispanic; Hispanic; other	No	S